

IMPERATIVES OF BIBLICAL RESPONSE TO PROSPERITY TEACHINGS FOR THE SPIRITUAL AWAKENING OF CONTEMPORARY CHRISTIANS*

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Abstract

The desire and pursuit for materialism among many contemporary Christians have found their way into churches in Nigeria, leading her into a deep spiritual sleep. This quest has left many Christians to jettison the fundamental doctrines of the Christian faith for another doctrine that accentuates the accumulation of earthly wealth, focusing on the here and now. Hence the need for spiritual awakening. To this end, the paper argues for imperatives of biblical response to prosperity teachings and its materialistic tendencies bedevilling the church. The goal is to reaffirm the doctrine of contentment by stressing the holistic teaching of the gospel message. Findings revealed that materialistic tendencies manifest in different forms, one of which is the erroneous teaching that God's children deserve the best of everything on earth. The paper, in its apologetic approach, submits that the Bible does not in any way affirm the accumulation of material possessions in this world at the expense of eternity; instead, it teaches contentment for all believers.

Keywords: Prosperity, Christian, Wealth, Contentment.

Introduction

The quest for materialism among many Christians in the contemporary church in Nigeria is fast, leading many to deep spiritual sleep and insensitivity. Hence, the need for the spiritual awakening of churches in Nigeria. Spiritual awakening suggests a situation when someone or something was previously in a state of spiritual sleep or slumber; the church, in this case, due to its wrong teachings, needed to be awakened or revived.¹ However, before the offshoot of the challenge of prosperity teachings in Nigeria, it could be recalled that a few decades ago, holiness was tantamount to poverty, penury and the like, and many Christians then never

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admired or did anything to acquire wealth because it was believed that being wealthy would lead one away from Christ. While that position does not align with Biblical teaching, it is pertinent to assert that the sudden shift from that erroneous mindset has led the church to the other extreme of materialism. Materialism, according to the Advanced Learners' English dictionary, "is a desire for wealth and material possessions with little interest in ethical or spiritual matters." The channel by which this desire is pursued in the church is through prosperity teachings or the prosperity gospel.

Unfortunately, pursuing materialism seems to have gotten to the extent that being poor as a Christian is now considered a sin among God's people. The biblical name for this quest is greed and covetousness,² and it commences when Christians compare themselves with unbelievers in achievements and wealth, leading them to lose their focus on Christ. Admittedly, "in many of our pulpits today, the preaching is centred on worldly achievements and material prosperity: houses and cars, success in business, money, health and happiness."³ That shows that the church's focus, both clergy and laity is now on material things and physical happiness at the expense of spiritual fervency and vibrancy. The challenge of prosperity teachings and its materialistic tendencies among many contemporary Christians, and its consequential lukewarm status of churches in Nigeria, demands a spiritual awakening. Hence, "many people follow Jesus today not because he is the bread of life but because they see him as the means to material prosperity"⁴ The churches in Nigeria seems to have forgotten the injunction of the Lord Jesus, "seek ye first the kingdom of God and his righteousness, and all these things shall be added unto you" (Matthew 6:33), and have twisted the verse as "seek ye first the things of this world and their fullness, and the kingdom of God shall be added unto you."⁵ Invariably, this has led the African church into deep spiritual sleep, and the urgent need arises for a spiritual awakening.

This paper present imperatives of biblical response to prosperity teachings for a spiritual awakening of contemporary Christians. The goal is to reaffirm the doctrine of contentment by upholding the holistic teaching of the gospel message. The paper discusses some prosperity teachings with materialistic tendencies; then it examines the Biblical response to the forms of prosperity teachings; reflects on Imperatives of Biblical response to prosperity teachings for Spiritual Awakening.

Materialism-Oriented Prosperity Teachings

The first form of prosperity teaching is the erroneous teaching which makes Christians believe that God's children deserve the best of everything on earth. Gordon Fee bolsters this position and maintains, "Because we are God's children, we should always go first-class – we should have the biggest and best, a Cadillac instead of a Volkswagen because this alone brings glory to God."⁶ That erroneous teaching drives many Christians to be materialistic and spiritually insensitive. So, when the church begins to teach that as God's children, they deserve the best in this world, they soon become greedy and covetous of what God has not graciously given.

The second form of prosperity teaching is the continuous shift from the holistic teaching of the truth of God's word to promoting wealth and prosperity teachings. Maxey and Ozodo maintain that "Popular teaching in much of the Nigerian church has fundamentally shifted ... from teaching the necessity for spiritual transformation characterised by holiness to teaching a form of transformation based on the evidence of health and wealth."⁷ The church is therefore sliding into materialism when the attention of the clergy is based only on physical prosperity and wealth creation. Some other begins with the reconstruction of the church auditorium, not necessarily because of an obvious need for more people to worship but to fit modern taste at the expense of evangelism and mission. That has led to deep spiritual sleep in areas of mission and evangelism.

The third form of prosperity teaching is when the clergy manipulates (or coerces) his congregation to give or, better put, empty their purses for the work of God. This is done using specific terminologies like ‘sowing and reaping generously,’ the ‘hundredfold returns,’ the ‘seed-faith principle,’ ‘that thou mayest prosper,’ ‘give, and it will be given to you,’ among others.⁸ These terms are products of inappropriate Biblical hermeneutics of some Bible passages used in backing them up. Such preachers and teachers would not exegete the text and put it in proper contextual perspective before application. Some Bible verses that materialistic preachers use include Mark 10:29 – 30; Gal. 6:7; 3 John 2; and Luke 6:38, among others. With these teachings, their members tend to jettison the biblical injunction of working to earn to believing in the sudden miracle of abundance.

The fourth form of prosperity teaching is advancing a doctrine that there are specific divine keys and principles to be operated in to be prosperous. Ajiboye corroborates it this way, “material prosperity and perfect health are God’s will for every Christian in this life and that there are divine keys or principles which, when followed, unlock and launch one into the realm of abundance and total well-being.”⁹ The emphasis is ‘here’ and ‘now.’ The people of God must succeed and prosper at all costs if they apply the appropriate divine principles. The question is, are there other principles the scriptures teach which should not be applied? Why is it only on earthly or physical prosperity? That emphasis has led many Christians into a deep spiritual sleep.

The fifth form of prosperity teaching the author like to mention is the promotion and practice of isolated truths of God’s word, which are usually misinterpreted. For instance, Fee, writing on the ill of the wealth gospel, explains that “the fault ... lies not with such isolated truths, but with the bottom line, which always comes back to one continual reaffirmation: God wills the (financial) prosperity of every one of his children.”¹⁰ Therefore, for a Christian to be live in poverty is to be outside God’s will; “it is to be living a Satan-defeated life.”¹¹ The

question is, which particular passage of the Bible teaches and emphasises this doctrine? Moreover, how does being poor though a Christian means living a defeated life? All these are fallacies. These shades imply that “any Christian that is poor or critically ill is operating outside God’s will for his or her life, which may be a consequence of his or her sin, ignorance or lack of adequate faith on his or her part.”¹² That perception has always led to frustration, depression and other negative issues. These are reasons many believers in many African churches today are still babes in the Spirit and are lacking the courage to stand for their faith in Christ.

Biblical Response to Materialism-Oriented Prosperity Teachings

In this section, biblical responses are presented to the forms of prosperity teachings mentioned above. The first form of prosperity teaching is the erroneous teaching that makes Christians believe that God’s children deserve the best of everything on earth. It should be asserted that there is no particular verse of the Bible which supports the view that God’s children deserve the best of everything on earth. Earthly prosperity for God’s children is never the focus of any passage. It instead teaches against it. For instance, Jesus in Matthew 6:19 – 21 cautions, “Do not store up for yourselves treasures on earth But store up for yourselves treasures in heaven For where your treasure is, there your heart will be also.” More so, the Bible teaches and warns against the accumulation of material possessions. This, it cautions concerning greed and covetousness. Jesus, in Luke 12:15, warns, “Watch out! Be on your guard against all kinds of greed; a man's life does not consist in the abundance of his possessions.”

Krehl explains covetousness as having a strong irresistible desire or possession or multiplication of possessions.¹³ Such strong desire, he maintains, “instead of aspiring to noble, high, and divine goods, will be brought to; the almost exclusive contemplation of earthly, immaterial things; and thus, instead of becoming gradually more closely united with God, will become more and more estranged from him.”¹⁴ Invariably, being covetous makes a Christian replace his/her genuine love for God with love for material things. Since the Bible affirms that

where the treasure is there, the heart is also, the heart of the covetous would not be with God, but with Mammon. Covetousness springs from greedy self-centeredness and an arrogant disregard for God's law. The Bible repeatedly warns against this sin (Matt 6:24; Luke 16:13; Josh. 7:21; Rom. 7:7; 2 Peter 2:10).

On the second form of prosperity teaching which is the continuous shift from the holistic teaching of the truth of God's word to promoting wealth and prosperity. One must maintain that Biblical teachings are holistic; it covers every aspect of human life without giving preference for one over another. It should be recalled that the Lord Jesus rebuked the teachers of the law and the Pharisees of this error in Matthew 23:23, "You give a tenth of your spices — mint, dill and cummin. But you have neglected the more important matters of the law — justice, mercy and faithfulness. You should have practised the latter without neglecting the former." By implication, no specific teaching of the Bible is superior to another, and none should be exalted more than the other. They are all to be taught, known, and practised in obedience. Again, the Ten Commandments God gave through Moses in Exodus 20 is a holistic instruction. They have an abiding significance for the contemporary church, for God's character is unchangeable. These laws originate from God and form His eternal character; their moral value cannot change as it emphasises obedience¹⁵ and is still relevant to the contemporary church. Therefore, holistic Biblical injunctions are still the best guidelines for practical daily living known to man.

Another response is to the third form of prosperity teaching that bothers on when the pastor manipulates (or coerces) his congregation to give or, better put, empty their purses for the work of God. Giving, otherwise regarded as a sacrifice in the Bible, especially to God, has always been an act of worship. God's love and giving are predicated on His mercy, and therefore in their every expression, they are unconditional. God loves, gives, and forgives unconditionally – no strings attached.¹⁶ It is on this premise that Fee argues that "human

response to divine grace is gratitude, which expresses itself in identical, unconditional love, giving, and forgiving.”¹⁷ Speaking on why sacrifice (giving)? Morris contends that “a prime reason was the promotion of fellowship with God, but there can be no doubt that in the Old Testament, the significant element was the putting of the sinful person right with God. Sacrifice was to make atonement Ex. 30:10; Lev. 1:4; 4:20 among others.”¹⁸ More also, the Bible does not uphold giving to God in order to get it back in multiple folds. Many of the scriptural passages used to buttress the deceptive giving by materialistic gospel ministers are usually quoted out of context.

The next response is to the fourth form of prosperity teaching, which advances a doctrine that there are specific divine keys and principles to be operated on to be prosperous. Contrary to this false teaching, willingness and obedience to all teachings are what the Bible affirms as the key to living in God’s blessings (Deut. 28:1 – 15; Isa. 1:19). Furthermore, one prominent position of the Bible on materialistic tendency is that it shows, with vivid examples, the sad end of covetous people, affirming that God detests it in all forms. One such character is Achan, son of Carmi, who became disobedient and coveted some of the accursed material God clearly warned against (Josh. 7:20 – 21 NIV). Besides the fact that Achan’s greed brought a great defeat to the army of Israel, making them lose thirty-six men among their soldiers, it also destroyed his entire household (cf. Josh. 7:24 – 26).

Other examples in the Bible of individuals who were disobedient to God and pursued material prosperity outside of God’s way include Gehazi, the servant of Elisha, who, because of greed and impatience, lied to acquire some material possessions from Naaman (2 Kings 5:20 – 27). Judas Iscariot, one Jesus’ disciples, jettisoned all the warning of the Lord Jesus Christ and employed the key of betrayal of His master to acquire some twenty pieces of silver (Matt. 26:14 – 15). Applying various methods to acquire prosperity contrary to God’s instructions and strict obedience to His commands is unacceptable. In fact, Apostle Paul labelled the sin as

idolatry (Col. 3:5); as a serious matter, he warned believers not to associate with a covetous brother (1 Cor. 5:10 – 11).¹⁹

The last response is to the fifth form of prosperity teaching, which is the promotion and practice of isolated truths of God's word, which are usually misinterpreted. What the Bible upholds and teaches is that God is the creator of both the rich and the poor, and it does not in any way condemn the poor or call them sinful. To be poor is "having little or no wealth and few or no possessions; lacking in financial or other resources."²⁰ The Bible holds that the poor will remain a part of society (Deut. 15:11; Matt. 26:11), and also instructs the righteous to show concern for them²¹ as God would personally take up their cause (Ps. 72:13; 132:15; Prov. 19:17 and Matt. 25:34 – 40). Jesus instructed that the poor should be invited when a feast is prepared (Luke 14:12-14; Gal. 2:10), and James warned against discrimination against the poor even among the believers in Christ (James 2:2 – 4). Besides, the poor are considered the people of God. While "poor" can be used simply to denote an economic condition,²² it is often used as a synonym for "people of God."²³ The poor widow who gave two copper coins is a notable example of piety that depends totally on God (Luke 21:1-4). The "poor" to whom Jesus promises the kingdom are disciples (Luke 6:20; Matt 5:3; cf. James 2:5). Thus, the people of God can be identified as the "poor" for various reasons: social and economic deprivation, voluntary poverty (cf. Matt. 19:23 – 30), persecution, and total dependence upon God for deliverance from every need (including deliverance from spiritual poverty; cf. Rev 3:17).²⁴

Furthermore, the Bible affirms contentment for Christians in all matters relating to material objects. Describing contentment, McClintock and Strong opine that "Contentment ... is a disposition of mind in which our desires are confined to what we enjoy without murmuring at our lot, or wishing ardently for more."²⁵ A closer look at this description reveals that there is no way one can be materialistic without throwing contentment into the garbage bin. Being content does not imply unconcern about self-welfare or that one should not have a sense of

anything distressing, nor does it give any countenance to idleness or prevent diligent endeavours from improving one's circumstances.²⁶ It implies, however, that one's desire for worldly goods is moderate; that one does not indulge in unnecessary care or use unlawful efforts to better oneself; but that one acquiesces with and makes the best of one's condition, whatever it be.

Implications of the Biblical Responses to Prosperity Teachings for Spiritual Awakening of Contemporary Christians

In the light of the preceding discussions, it is germane to enumerate some imperatives of the materialistic tendencies occasioned by prosperity teachings for the spiritual awakening of the church and Christians.

At first, Christians should reject any teaching that encourages wealth accumulation on earth without eternity in view. When they sense that they are gradually becoming covetous, they should stand their ground against such teachings. This is because prosperity teachings and their materialistic tendencies weaken a Christian's living faith in Christ Jesus and make him/her complacent about the consciousness of God. Eyre contends, "materialism blunts a living faith. A vibrant sense of the presence of God becomes dead orthodoxy."²⁷ This implies that the more a Christian begins to live with the mentality of deserving the best of things on earth, his/her spiritual vibrancy depletes. Then one life experience in Christ becomes empty, and the authenticity of such Christian life becomes a shadow of itself; hence the individual falls into a deep sleep. If one cannot see it, taste it, smell it or measure it, then one doubts that it is real. Therefore, one comes to doubt that God is real.²⁸

Secondly, believers in Christ should stay clear from preachers whose teaching is continuously shifting away from the holistic teaching (involving various aspects of the Christian life) of the truth of God's word to promoting wealth and prosperity. Biblical messages and teachings are holistic and do not prefer one over the other. Life is not all about being

prosperous; other aspects of the Christian life should be developed. The imperative of this is consequent to the fact that materialism “bred Christians that are materialistic in their approach to life while remaining spiritually bankrupt.”²⁹ This is because only a half-truth negates the wholesome gospel of Jesus Christ, which applies to all areas of life.³⁰ Anyone living his/her Christian life based on these kinds of teachings and beliefs will never come to spiritual maturity. Being materialistic conscious does not give room for the genuine pursuit of God’s will in all human endeavours. What matters to the individual will be what benefit will he/she derives from every opportunity; whether pleasing to God or not does not matter.

Thirdly, Christians are encouraged to engage their rationality when manipulated to empty their purses for the course of the gospel. Any giving in the church that transcends voluntary and willful giving of one’s resources in worship is a false teaching. Because “the craving for personal peace and affluence afflicts us all The message of God’s offer of life to a fallen world loses its impelling force, and the church, like the rest of the culture, is pulled into a treadmill life going nowhere.”³¹ Being materialistic hampers, believers urge to share the love of Christ in society because their attention has been shifted to self and personal happiness, which is usually self-seeking and gratifying. This attitude does not allow for expressing the love of Christ to the unbelievers.

Fourthly, church members are enjoined to be alert in watching out for total obedience to Biblical instructions and not just a segment. There are gospel ministers that emphasized obedience to some sections of the Bible while downplaying some others commands of God. Therefore, any church that does not reiterate to its members the urge to make adequate preparation for eternity by being submissive to all Biblical doctrines is not a church. Thus, they should leave such churches if they have eternity in view. The reason remains that materialism makes believers in Christ to be preoccupied with earthly things alone at the expense of planning for eternity. “All our time, energy and thoughts are focused on the physical aspects of life. We

become practical materialists.”³² Though Christians know that the Bible teaches that there is more to life, how they live shows that they have adopted the creed of the dragon of materialism, “matter is all that matters.”³³ The desire to live in affluence, build mansions and ride luxurious cars focuses the Christian’s attention to the world while losing the keen interest in eternal values.

Finally, the awareness of Christians should be drawn to any form of segregation of members by status and other means of division. Everyone should be considered as God’s children who have come to worship God alone and not any other thing. Wiersbe argues that being materialistic leads believers into the “worship of health, wealth and happiness”,³⁴ making physical things a god. Goudzwaard argues that “we know from the scripture that both persons and societies can put their faith in things and forces which their own hands have made. In their pursuit of prosperity, salvation, health, protection and so forth, people sooner or later create gods.”³⁵ His emphasis is that gods never leave their makers alone. The reason is that people put themselves in a position of dependence on their gods; invariably, the moments come when these things or forces gain the upper hand in the control of their lives.³⁶ That argument of Goudzwaard agrees with Adeleye, who narrated the open confession of Jim Bakker, the founder of PTL ministry and Heritage USA, whose empire was said to have collapsed in 1987.³⁷ Adeleye quoted Bakker to have conceded and confessed in an interview, “I allowed the PTL ministry to grow in such a way that the building at Heritage USA became almost more important than the message of Jesus Christ. My vision was so important that I worked day and night to keep this monster alive.”³⁸

Aligning and subjecting oneself as a Christian to prosperity teachings with its tendencies makes one go into profound spiritual sleep that will never allow a Christian to live up to the reality of what God has sent the individual to pursue with his/her life on earth. It is saddening that many African churches today have fallen prey to this snare that is focused on

the accumulation of wealth here on earth at the expense of the basics of the Christian faith, especially discipleship, genuine worship of God, passionate mission and evangelism. Though they claimed to be doing missions, the spiritual shallowness of their members and their inability to stand for Christ in the face of daunting life challenges are pointers to the rotten state.

Conclusion

The paper has shown that prosperity teachings with their materialistic tendencies manifest in many churches today in various forms. It is also apparent that the Bible does not uphold any of the erroneous teachings revealed in the Biblical response discussed. Therefore, since the Bible does not in any way affirm the accumulation of material possessions in this world at the expense of eternity, Christians should desist from teachings that align with such. They are to uphold and imbibe contentment for all believers in obedience to the holistic doctrines of the Bible.

Endnotes

¹ Kristi Walker, “What Is a Spiritual Awakening and Are We Experiencing One Now?” 4 May 2020 <https://www.christianity.com/wiki/christian-terms/spiritual-awakening-and-are-we-experiencing-one-now.html> (Accessed 20 January 2022)

² Covetousness is “an intense desire to possess something (or someone) that belongs to another person ... Covetousness springs from a greedy self-centeredness and an arrogant disregard of God's law. The Bible repeatedly warns against this sin (cf. Josh. 7:21; Rom. 7:7; 2 Peter 2:10). (See; *Nelson's Illustrated Bible Dictionary*. Herbert Lockyer, Sr. ed. (Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers, 1986), 260.)

³ Michael Otieno Maura, “True and False Prosperity” in *Prosperity? Seeking the True Gospel*. Michael Otieno Maura, Conrad Mbewe, Ken Mbugua, John Piper and Wayne Grudem. (Buruku: ACTS, 2015), 34.

⁴ Femi Bitrus Adeleye, *Preachers of a Different Gospel: A Pilgrim's Reflection on Contemporary Trends in Christianity*. (Buruku: ACTS, 2001), 77.

⁵ Adeleye, 77.

⁶ Gordon Fee, *The Disease of Health and Wealth Gospels*. (Vancouver: Regent College Publishing, 2006), 9.

⁷ Gary Maxey, and Peter Ozodo. *The Seduction of the Nigerian Church*. (Ipaja: WATS Publications, 2017), 46.

⁸ Bruce Barron, *The Health and Wealth Gospel: What's Going on Today in a Movement that has shaped the Faith of millions?* Downers Grove: IVP, 1987, 89 – 93. (cf. Femi Bitrus Adeleye, *Preachers of a Different Gospel: A Pilgrim's Reflection on Contemporary Trends in Christianity*. (Buruku: ACTS, 2001), 81 – 86)

⁹ Abraham A. Ajiboye, *Christian Suffering and Prosperity Gospel*. (Kaduna: Able Publishers, 2013), 16.

¹⁰ Fee, 8.

¹¹ Fee, 8.

¹² Ajoboye, 16.

¹³ N. T. Krehl, "Covetousness" in *Mcclintock and Strong Encyclopedia*. John Mcclintock, and James Strong, eds. (Grand Rapids: Baker Book House Company, 2006) (Softcopy).

¹⁴ Krehl.

¹⁵ "Commandment, Ten" in *Nelson's Illustrated Bible Dictionary*. Herbert Lockyer, Sr. ed. (Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers, 1986), 246.

¹⁶ Fee, 16.

¹⁷ Fee.

¹⁸ L. L. Morris, "Sacrifice" in *New Dictionary of Theology*. Sinclair B. Ferguson, David F. Wright, and J. I. Packer, eds. (Downers Grove: Intervarsity Press, 1988), 608.

¹⁹ "Covetousness" in *Nelson's Illustrated Bible Dictionary*, 260.

²⁰ "Poor" in *Nelson's Illustrated Dictionary*, 860.

²¹ "Poor" in *Nelson's Illustrated Dictionary*.

²² Cf.: The Merismus "rich and poor," which is used to describe the totality of humankind; e.g., Rev. 13:16; Ps. 49:2; Ruth 3:10.

²³ D. E. Holwerda, "Poor" in *The International Standard Bible Encyclopedia, Volume Three*. Geoffrey W. Bromiley, ed. (Grand Rapids: Williams B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 1979), 905.

²⁴ Holwerda, 906.

²⁵ John McClintock, and James Strong, "Contentment" in *McClintock and Strong Encyclopedia*. (Grand Rapids: Baker Book House Company, 2006) (Soft Copy).

²⁶ McClintock and Strong.

²⁷ Stephen D. Eyre, *Defeating the Dragons of the World: Resisting the Seduction of False Values*. (Downers Grove: IVP, 1987), 28.

²⁸ Eyre, 28.

²⁹ Ajiboye, 19.

³⁰ Ajiboye, 18.

³¹ Eyre, 12.

³² Eyre, 28.

³³ Eyre.

³⁴ Warren W. Wiersbe, *The Integrity Crisis*. (Nashville: Oliver Nelson, 1988), 52.

³⁵ Bob Goudzwaard, *Idols of Our Time*. (Downers Grove: IVP, 1984), 13.

³⁶ Goudzwaard, 13.

³⁷ Adeleye, 81.

³⁸ Adeleye.

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